

Big Data Analysis Reveals Source of Oscillatory Happy Sadness Outbreak in IChemE Process Management and Control Subject Interest Group

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of behalf of all the IChemE PMCSIG

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Abstract: Detailed analysis reveals source of mystery oscillatory mood outbreak in influential committee.

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1. INTRODUCTION

A normally productive and carefree team of control professionals suddenly experienced an outbreak of happy, sad then happy again behaviour in a normally efficient committee.

Detailed analysis by a dedicated task force of colleagues revealed the underlying cause to be the retirement of Nina Thornhill.

Key discoveries included:

“Nina, what a great contribution you’ve made to control & automation. Not only training the next generations but also working closely with industry so you knew the practical side of what was needed. Great to see your ideas continually being taken up by vendors, particularly through your collaborations, I heard it mentioned by SEEQ just the other day.”

“Nina joined the Committee in June 2003 when she was a Senior Lecturer at UCL and Andrew Odgen-Swift was Chair. She took over the Chair from Andrew in March 2013 by which time she was ABB RAE Professor at Imperial and stayed as Chair until a charismatic replacement took over in November 2016.

When Nina started as chair, she introduced the concept of Vice Chairs as a way of sharing the pressure on the Chair.

Nina did a huge amount for the SIG. Rarely missed a Committee Meeting, acted as webmaster, organised day meetings and was active in bidding for research projects and the proposals for a Process Automation Academy.

As Chair, she was very effective at getting things done.”

“I first met Nina when she became a member of the committee of the Process Management and Control Special Interest Group (PMCSIG) of the IChemE in 2003. She quickly established herself as a thoughtful, considerate and committed member who earned the respect of all about her.

During 2007, Nina moved from University College to Imperial College. Shortly thereafter I approached her about becoming the External Examiner for the MSc in Process Automation at Newcastle University. This was the programme offered through the Partnership in Automation and Control Training (PACT):

she accepted and was EE from 2007/08 until 2009/10. In that capacity I had much interaction with Nina. Again it was of a positive nature: I found her to be consistently both careful and thorough, and her criticisms were always cast in a constructive vein!

Nina was instrumental in the MSc programme moving to Imperial College during 2014/15 and she took over from myself as Course Director until 2016/17. Her planning and attention to detail was meticulous, not just the admin but also on the teaching front too. Her contribution to the programme over many years was significant and is greatly appreciated.

Thankyou Nina,”

“Nina approaches any task from the perspective doing it well. She is hard working, efficient and great fun to be with. Her academic contribution is there in so many papers but her wonderful outlook of life and occasionally impish behaviour taught me that hard work tempered with fun and love provides joy to all”

Nina, everyone on the committee are delighted to see you head off on a wonderful, fulfilling retirement. We are also sad that our committee no longer benefits from the insight, skill and preparation you brought to each meeting and in every task you committed to. In the end, our happiness beats our sadness hands down.”

Nina, the entire PMCSIG wishes you many years of happy retirement as you explore strange new worlds and seek out the many fun things to do and think about in this beautiful world.

Many many thanks Nina.